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SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF DRUG ABUSE ON STUDENTS OF TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN KOGI STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

Drug abuse has been prevalent among students in tertiary institutions and this is attributed to factors such as experimental curiosity; lack of parental supervision; personality issues due to the socio-economic conditions of the students. This study was therefore aimed at assessing the socio-psychological effects of drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria. To guide the study, five specific objectives with corresponding research questions were formulated, while five null hypotheses were also postulated. The study utilized descriptive survey design with a sample size of 396 which comprises of students of all tertiary institutions in Kogi State who have enrolled for 2021/2022 academic session. Data were collected through the use of semi-structured questionnaire. Data collected were analysed using frequencies, percentages with the help of Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) version and all the hypotheses stated were tested with one-way ANOVA. The study found out that larger percentage of respondents across the tertiary institutions did not have knowledge of drug abuse and also not aware of the socio-psychological effects of drug abuse. It further revealed that most of the respondents use drugs daily, and that they use drugs because it gives them confidence and puts them on high morals. Specifically, it was discovered that vast of types of drugs abused included; Indian hemp, Tobacco, Cocaine and morphine, Heroin and Caffeine, Tramadol, Codeine, alcohol-ethanol, Tranquilizers etc. The study further revealed that so many factors are responsible for drug abuse among students in tertiary institutions in Kogi State some of which are places of residence, income level, peer group influence, religion, education level etc. It was also discovered that the social effects of drug abuse include dropping out of school, shame and guilt, embarrassment, sleeplessness or insomnia etc. while the psychological effects of drug abuse include mental illness, heart attacks, anger, frustration, anxiety, etc. The following recommendations were made based on the findings. Government through the management of the tertiary institutions should engage students in order to inform their knowledge of drug abuse as well as create awareness of the socio-psychological effects of drug abuse. Government through the management of the tertiary institutions should prohibit an act that could lead to sales of vast types of drugs commonly abused by the students especially Tramadol in order to cushion its socio-psychological effects among the students.

Keywords:

Drug Abuse, Socio-Psychological Effects, Students, Tertiary Institutions, Kogi State

Introduction

The misuse of drugs is reported to negatively impact on society, family, health, and life in general, thus constituting an epidemic worldwide. The group mostly at risk regarding the abuse of drugs is the youth (Balogun, 2020). There are recent indications of an increasing trend globally of students in tertiary institutions indulging in this unhealthy habit of drug abuse. The period of study for a lot of students at the university or other tertiary institutions is also regarded as a period of independence from family supervision, forming of new relationships, acquiring new habits, making independent decisions, balancing life and academic pressures and becoming generally exposed to various values and cultures (Balogun, 2020). This author further noted that newly acquired independence often result in influencing youths to yield to unhealthy behaviours such as drinking, smoking and use of hard drugs. Ogunsola et al., (2020) pointed out that the abuse of substances such as drug is on the increase in African countries.

Substances such as heroin, inhalants, tranquilizers, cocaine, alcohol and tobacco which have become quite popular among higher educational institutions. The abuse of drugs has contributed to psychosocial problems among youths. Nigeria, an African country is not exempted from these social problem rampaging higher institutions as evidenced (Ogunsola et al., 2020). Ogunsola et al., (2020) compared Nigeria with other third world countries and declared Nigeria to be high in the ranks of countries with high number of dangerous drug users. They maintained that the reason for the availability and prevalence of psychoactive substances was attributed to traffickers using Nigeria as a channel in the transportation of drugs from South East-Asia and South America to European countries. Other contributory factors for this prevalence include peer pressure and the desire of students to explore and experiment.

The use of drugs has been part of human existence right from time immemorial. Hence, there is nothing wrong when human beings use drugs, especially when they are properly administered. Drugs that are properly administered have served as medical function. For example, herbs, roots, bark, leaves and plants, all these have been used to relieve pains and help control diseases. Today, thousands of the drugs are used (Lawal, 2019). If properly used, they tend to have immense value to man like disease treatment and correction of body abnormalities. However, if not properly used, drugs can have serious consequences on the human system. The most serious consequences are from the abuse of drugs. Drug abuse is a major public health problem all over the world (World Health Organization, WHO, 2019). The use and abuse of drugs by students of tertiary institutions have become one of the most disturbing health related phenomena in Nigeria and other parts of the world (National Drug Law Enforcement Agency [NDLEA], 2019).

Several students in tertiary institutions experience mental health problem, either temporarily or for a long period (Oliha, 2014). The health of students in tertiary institutions is a key factor in the promotion and preservation of the health of the population as a whole because it determines the overall level of population health in the short term (Tsvetkova & Antonova, 2013). However, there seem to be an increasing incidence of drug abuse amongst students in tertiary institutions as NDLEA recorded that 55.9% of the students were engaged in drug abuse in 2017 and 69.3% in 2019. In fact, despite the efforts of concerned bodies such as; NDLEA to curb this menace, the percentage of students in tertiary institutions involved in drug abuse increase to 72.4% in 2020. These implied that students in tertiary institutions are the most susceptible to drug use amongst different youth groups in Nigeria because most of them live outside the watch of their parents or guardians (Haladu, 2013)

Drug abuse had been prevalent among students in tertiary institutions as this is attributed to factors such as experimental curiosity; that is curiosity to experiment the unknown facts about drugs thus motivates students into drug use, lack of parental supervision that is; many parents have no time to supervise their sons and daughters, personality issues due to the socio-economic conditions of the students (Timothy & Usman, 2020). Obviously, the social and economic status of most Nigerians is below average. Hence, poverty is widely spread, increase in broken homes and unemployment (Shehu & Idris, 2018). To this end, the effects of drug abuse cannot be overemphasized as it results to alcohol-related problems like; liver cirrhosis, pancreatic, peptic ulcer, tuberculosis, hypertension and neurological disorder as well as sexual transmitted diseases like; HIV/AIDs and Syphilis, amongst others (Shehu & Idris, 2018).

Statement of the Problem

Drugs had long been recognized in extant studies as substances capable of bringing about a change in the biological function of an individual through its chemical actions, while modifying perceptions, cognition, mood, behaviour and general body functions (Balogun, 2016). However, recent outrage in the country points to the very fact that most drugs have become severally abused, through wrongful and inappropriate application, thereby resulting in a national menace coupled with social and psychological effects especially among students in tertiary institutions.

In order to address this social ill in the society, it became a thing of worldwide concern and education to create awareness about the dangers of drug abuse (Ken, 2019). Despite the awareness on drug abuse through seminars, symposia, workshop and conferences, most of the students in tertiary institutions fail to utilize the outcome of the awareness to restrain from drug abuse. Thus, Godwin (2020) submitted drug abuse as a responsible factor for high level of anti-social, psychological, economic and health problems confronting most students in tertiary institutions as it accounts for majority of the criminal activities. Arguably, there is no consensus among scholars on the social and psychological effects of drug abuse among students in tertiary institutions. Whereas Okoza and Aluede (2019) asserted that dropping out of school, embarrassment and relationship problem were the social effects of drug abuse among students in tertiary institutions. While Ezeifu (2021), Udoh, Chukwueke et al., (2020) disagreed that the social effects of drug abuse among students in tertiary institutions include poor academic work ethics or academic performance and difficulty maintaining personal hygiene. On the other hand, some of the previous scholars disagreed on the psychological effects of drug abuse among students in tertiary institutions as Haladu (2013) submitted that the psychological effects include mental illness, heart attacks, anger, frustration, anxiety, worry, stress and depression, sleeplessness, less of coordination and temporary sense of joy. While Aremu, et al. (2018) considered these effects to include panic disorder, memory loss, difficulty in concentration Lethargy or loss of interest and increase heart rate/ palpitation. Furthermore, other studies by authors such as Godwin and Daniel (2021) submitted that some students in tertiary institutions abuse drugs to aid academic performance. Similarly, Bode (2019) argued that some students also abuse drugs to subdue depression. Meanwhile, Joseph and Caleb (2020) asserted that drug abuse make some students completely restless, and keep others highly aggressive. In the literature, most of the previous studies on drug abuse by scholars such as; Haladu (2013), Oliha (2014), Onofa et al. (2016), Aremu et al. (2018) were carried out in secondary schools and higher institutions of learning elsewhere with little or no attention given to comparative studies on tertiary institutions in Kogi State whose most students might indulge in drug abuse because of the reported cases of examination malpractices and cultism among other social problems. Hence, this study attempted to bridge the gap by examining the socio-psychological effects of drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following questions guided the study:

- i. What is the extent of students of tertiary educational institutions' awareness of the socio-psychological effects of drug abuse in Kogi State, Nigeria?
- ii. What are the types of drugs commonly abused by students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria?
- iii. What are the factors responsible for drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria?
- iv. What are the social effects of drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria?
- v. What are the psychological effects of drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria?

Aim and objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to examine the socio-psychological effects of drug abuse among students of tertiary institution in Kogi State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to;

- i. Determine the extent of students of tertiary educational institutions socio-psychological effects of awareness of drug abuse in Kogi State, Nigeria.
- ii. Identify the type of drugs commonly abused by students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria.
- iii. Identify the factors responsible for drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions' in Kogi State, Nigeria.
- iv. Assess the social effects of drug abuse on students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria.
- v. Examine the psychological effects of drug abuse on students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

The following study hypotheses in null forms were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: Awareness of socio-psychological effects of drug abuse do not deter its usage among students of tertiary educational institution in Kogi State, Nigeria

H₀₂: There are no gender differences in commonly abused drugs among students of tertiary educational institution in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Ho₃: Availability and accessibility of drugs do not influence its abuse among students in tertiary educational institution in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Ho₄: Drug abuse does not significantly lead to social effects among students in tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Ho₅: Drug abuse does not significantly lead to psychological effects among students in tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

This research work has both practical and theoretical significance in the following ways:

- ✓ Informing prevention and intervention strategies: The study could help educational institutions develop more effective drug abuse prevention programs and targeted interventions.
- ✓ Improving support services: Findings of this study will guide the enhancement of counseling and mental health services for students struggling with drug abuse.
- ✓ Policy development: The results from this research work could inform institutional policies makers on drug use, disciplinary procedures, and support mechanisms.
- ✓ Resource allocation: The study may justify increased funding for drug abuse prevention and treatment programs in tertiary education settings by government at all levels.
- ✓ Expanding knowledge: The study would contribute to the existing body of research on drug abuse by serving as reference materials to future researchers, specifically in the context of higher education.
- ✓ Model development: Findings from this study may lead to new or refined theoretical models explaining the relationship between tertiary education, psychological factors, and drug abuse.
- ✓ Cross-disciplinary insights: The study could likewise bridge gaps between psychology, sociology, and education research, potentially leading to new interdisciplinary approaches.

Scope of the Study

The study focuses on socio-psychological effects of drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions. The study was carried out among three selected tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria. These three tertiary institutions covered the three senatorial districts in Kogi State respectively. These include; Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba in Kogi East, Kogi State Polytechnic, Lokoja in Kogi West and Federal College of Education, Okene in Kogi Central.

Literature Review

Relevant literature for this study were reviewed in accordance with the aim and objectives of the study and under the following subheadings:

Conceptual Reviews

The following concepts were reviewed for this study:

Drug

According to Fawa (2013) drug is viewed as any substance, which is used for treatment or prevention of a disease in man and animals. Drug refers to a substance that could bring about a change in the biological function through its chemical actions (Okoye, 2018). It is also considered as a substance that modifies perceptions, cognition, mood, behaviour and general body functions (Balogun, 2016). Drug alters the body functions either positively or otherwise depending on the body composition of the user, the type of drug used, the amount used and whether used singly or with other drugs at the same time. Drug is any psychoactive substance that can alter the way the mind or body works, regardless of legal status or medical approval.

There are two main ways to define drugs. First, a distinction may be drawn between medicines, which are medically sanctioned psychoactive substances used for clinical purposes, and drugs, which are controlled substances whose use is not sanctioned either by law or by medical practitioners. Second, drugs can be classified according to their pharmacological make up and attributed psychoactive effects (Nutt et al., 2010).

Drug Abuse

According to Haladu (2013) the term drug abuse is conceptualized as excessive and persistent self-administration of a drug without regard to the medically or culturally accepted patterns. It could also be viewed as the use of a drug to the extent that it interferes with the health and social function of an individual. Wada (2014) viewed drug abuse as the non-medical use of a drug that interferes with a healthy and productive life Manbe (2018) viewed drug abuse as the excessive, maladaptive or addictive use of drugs for non-medical purpose. Abdulahi (2019) viewed drug abuse as the use of drugs to the extent that interferes with the health and social function of an individual. In essence, drug abuse may be defined as the arbitrary overdependence or misuse of one particular drug with or without a prior medical diagnosis from qualified health practitioners. It can also be viewed as the unlawful overdose in the use of drug(s).

The term drug abuse is used to describe any licit or illicit substance that has an effect on the structure and functioning of the brain when it is taken wrongly. It includes alcohol, tobacco, medicine, Indian hemp, cocaine and other illegal substances (Haladu, 2013). Therefore, drugs can be legal or illegal; they can be helpful or harmful, depending on the type and the usage or mode of administration. Young people use drugs as a way of rebelling against parents or authority, to feel like adults, to fit in and belong to a group of other youths, to satisfy their curiosity, and to simply derive pleasure from the short-term effects of drugs. Abusers with underlying social or psychological problems are particularly at high risk for drug abuse (Shehu & Idris, 2018).

Socio-Psychological Effects of Drug Abuse among Students of Tertiary Educational Institution

The socio-psychological effect of drug abuse is evident in social and academic lives of drug abusers as it leads to declining grades, absenteeism, and potential for dropping out of school as well as leads in low level of commitment to education, among others (Ezeifu, 2021). Also, Okafor (2019) noted that students who majorly involved in drug abuse face socio-psychological issue like low self-esteem among their equals. Mba (2018) was of the view that due to drug like tobacco, it causes stimulation of heart and narrowing of blood vessels, producing hypertension, headache, loss of appetite, nausea and delayed growth of the fetus. It also aggravates or causes sinusitis, bronchitis, cancer, strokes, and heart attack. Also stimulants leads to lethargy, irritability, exaggerated self-confidence, damage nose

linings, sleeplessness, and psychiatric complications. Inhalants causes anemia, damage kidney and stomach bleeding while Narcotics causes poor perception, constipation, cough, suppression, vomiting, drowsiness and sleep, unconsciousness and death. Nnachi (2017) observed increased absenteeism and drop outs as one of the socio-psychological effect of drug abuse among students. Most psychoactive drugs affect the decision making process of students, their creative thinking and the development of necessary life and social skills. Drugs also interfere with an individual's awareness of their unique potential and thus their interest in their career development (Abdulahi, 2019). In the vein, Kanmodi (2020) pointed at health consequences of drug abuse to include engagement in crime, strained relationships and job loss.

Commonly Abused Drugs among Students of Tertiary Educational Institution

Majority of the students ignorantly depend on one form of drug or the other (such as Tobacco, Indian hemp, cocaine, morphine, Heroine, Alcohol, ephedrine, Madras, Caffeine, Glue, Barbiturates and Amphetamines) for their various daily activities (Oshikoya & Alli, 2016). Particularly, cannabis abusers are mostly young Nigerian men, including students, who have been deprived of parental supervision and warmth from infancy. Okoza and Aluede (2019) identified drugs substances commonly abused to include; alcohol, kolanut, tobacco, cannabis, Librium, dexamphetamine, reactivan, mandrax, Chinese capsule, cocaine and Lysergic acid Diethylamide (LSD). Udoh et al. (2020) observed it to include; alcohol-ethanol, tobacco, tramadol to be commonly abused by students. Marygoretty and Adhiambo (2021) indicated that most of the students used Tobacco, Miraa, Cocaine, Tranquilizers, Kuber and Marijuana. However, Oluyemi et al. (2019), identified these drugs to include; alcohol, tobacco, Cocaine, Coffee, Codeine, tranquilizer and Inhalants in that order. Bawa (2015) viewed most commonly abused substance was Marijuana and the least abused was cocaine, the reasons were availability and affordability of these substances. Alcohol was not commonly abused due to religious prohibition.

Factors Responsible for Drug Abuse among Students of Tertiary Institutions

Factors such as; experimental curiosity, lack of parental supervision and socio-economic conditions of the students are responsible for drug abuse among students in tertiary institutions (Aremu et al., 2018). Factor associated with drug abuse are numerous. However, factors such as place of residence, location of students, income, peer group influence, level of school security management were considered as major factors influencing drug abuse among students according to Afolabi (2017). In the study by Kuku and Odusanya (2015); Olurunfemi and Faleke (2020) factors that trigger drug abuse included education level and religion, shame of disclosing their problem to the doctor, ignorance, cultural and socio-economic issues are the reasons for increase in drug abuse in Nigeria. Other factors include; availability of medication at home, cost effective, ease of access to drugs and poverty (Yakubu, 2017).

Numerous factors are implicated as possible causes for the act of drug abuse Gray et al., (2002), opined that such factors could be social, physical or psychological. One of the strongest social reasons for people under involvement in drug abuse is peer group. Both teenager and adults are involved. Such peer influence is characterized by the desire to be accepted among friends or in social circumstance. Many of the students, who use hard drug, obtain them from friends in the same school or neighbouring schools. Such drugs are used at social gathering or when students have symptoms of sickness or stay awake during examination (Gray, 2012).

Empirical Reviews on the Social and Psychological Effects of Drug Abuse

Ezeifu (2021) investigated social effects of drug abuse among tertiary students in Nigeria. The study utilized primary data. The study specifically examined the effects drug abuse has on the social and academic lives of students as well as the factors that necessitate drug abuse among students. The study utilized survey research design. The study sample of size 880 constituted students from different academic level of study in selected states. The study used descriptive statistics of simple percentage method of analysis. The result indicated that several factors lead to drug abuse of which predominant among which are anxiety, depression, peers influence, among others. The study also indicated that drug abuse has effect of social and academic lives of drug abusers as it leads to declining grades, absenteeism, and potential for dropping out of school as well as leads in low level of commitment to education, among others. Finally, the study revealed that drug abuse had a negative effect on the users. The study recommended that there should be constant reminder to the students of the dangers of drug abuse and its implications to their studies and lives.

Marygoretty and Adhiambo (2021) investigated the effects and causes of drug use and abuse on the performance indicators among secondary school students in Teso South Constituency, Kenya. The study used primary data. Krejcie and Morgan's formula was used to select 192 students and data was collected from the field using questionnaires. The data analyzed using percentages. Results indicated that most of the students used Tobacco, Miraa, Cocaine, Tranquilizers, Kuber and Marijuana.

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Kanmodi (2020) determined the effects and pattern of drug abuse, as well as assessed the health and socioeconomic impact on students in School of Health Technology (SHT), in Jega, Kebbi State, Nigeria. Questionnaire was administered to 254 students in order to collect data which was analyzed using the SPSS Version 20 software. The study found that most of the respondents who disclosed a positive history of drug abuse had directly or indirectly suffered socio-economic and health consequences such as engagement in crime, strained relationships and job loss.

Ebelechukwu et al. (2020) assessed statistical analysis of the effect of drug abuse on academic performance in Wukari. The study employed primary data. The data were collected through distribution of questionnaires. Chi-square was used for data analysis. The result revealed that drug abuse had effect on students' academic performance in Wukari.

Udoh et al., (2020) evaluated Curbing drug/substance abuse among students in Universities in Nigeria. The study utilized descriptive survey research design using the final year students of University of Uyo. A total of 1407 students were selected while accidental sampling technique was adopted in selecting 70 students, which represents 5% of the population. Questionnaire was used for data collection. Data generated were analyzed using the descriptive statistics of frequency counts,

mean scores and standard deviations. The result of the study revealed that Alcohol-ethanol, tobacco, tramadol, were found to be abused. The study recommended intensified efforts by librarians in bringing to the knowledge of the students the dangers of drug/substance abuse and how to avoid them.

Okafor (2019) examined the causes and the social implications of drug abuse on undergraduate students in University of Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey design and a simple random sampling technique was used to select the respondents from the University of Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria for the study. The study used simple percentage and t-statistic method of data analysis. The instrument used was a questionnaire and it was revealed from the findings of the study that; students majorly involved in drug abuse because they needed to cope with their academic challenges; low self-esteem was a major consequence of drug abuse; based on gender and faculty/department, there were no significant differences.

Oluyemi et al. (2019) examined substance abuse and treatment among students in an institution of higher learning in Nigeria. A total of 40 consenting participants were involved in the study while primary data was gathered through questionnaire administration. The result showed that Indian hemp was the substance mostly abused by the study population closely followed by Alcohol (40.0%), tobacco smoking (25.0%), Cocaine (25.0%), Coffee (10.0%), Codeine (10.0%), Tranquilizer (10.0%) and Inhalants (10.0%) in that order. The study recommended that social work departments be created in all schools in Nigeria at all level to attend to the welfare needs of students especially in behavioural problems such as substance abuse and addiction.

Okoza and Aluede (2019) conducted a study on extent of drug abuse among students of AmbrosAlli University, Ekpoma, Nigeria. A total of 414 students drawn through multi stage proportionate sampling technique were used to select the participants from the entire students population of 13740 students currently enrolled in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma. The instrument used for the study was Pela's (1989) modified version of the student drug use questionnaire published by the World Health Organization. The first part of the questionnaire had information on personal data. The other sections had items eliciting information on the types of substance use, the frequency of use and reasons for use of the substance. Substances included in the survey were alcohol, kolanut, tobacco, cannabis, Librium, dexamphetamine, reactivan, mandrax, Chinese capsule, cocaine and Lysergic acid Diethylamide (LSD). This instrument was validated by two experts in psychology and education. The aim was to ensure that the items in the instrument are capable of eliciting responses to answer the research questions. To test for reliability of the instrument, a pre-test was conducted on a sample of 30 students of University of Benin, Benin city, Nigeria The split- half method yielded a correlation index of 79. The instrument was administered by the principal author with the aid of research assistants in the selected departments. The completed copies of the questionnaires were collected on the spot and a high percentage return was recorded. Data were analyzed using percentages and frequency counts. This study found that students in the university abuse hard drugs and that 'to feel good, 'availability,' 'parents' and 'siblings' influences and other factors predispose university students to abuse drugs. The study further revealed that the use of drugs among our students is assuming a dangerous dimension.

Mba (2018) examined the effect of drug abuse among students in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The study utilized both primary and secondary data. The primary data was generated using key informant interview which included 15 informants who were lecturers from three randomly selected institutions in Nigeria. The secondary data were based on existing literature while the descriptive content analysis was used to analyze the data. The study revealed that the negative effects of drug abuse on the body

chemistry as follows; alcohol-related problems includes; physical problems e.g liver cirrhosis, pancreatic, peptic ulcer, tuberculosis, hypertension, neurological disorder and mental retardation for the fetus in the womb, growth, deficiency, delayed motor development. Craniofacial abnormalities, limbs abnormalities and cardiac deficits. Psychiatric e.g pathological drunkenness, suicidal behavior. Socially-broken homes, increased crime rate, sexual offences, homicide and sexually transmitted diseases. The study also revealed that due to drug abuse, tobacco causes stimulation of heart and narrowing of blood vessels, producing hypertension, headache, loss of appetite, nausea and delayed growth of the fetus. It also aggravates or causes sinusitis, bronchitis, cancer, strokes, and heart attack. Also stimulants leads to lethargy, irritability, exaggerated self-confidence, damage nose linings, sleeplessness, and psychiatric complications. Inhalants causes anemia, damage kidney and stomach bleeding while Narcotics causes poor perception, constipation, cough, suppression, vomiting, drowsiness and sleep, unconsciousness and death.

Theoretical Framework: Social Influence Theory

This study was premised on social influence theory. This theory was propounded by Albert Bandura (1977). This theory is derived from the premise that adolescents who abuse drugs do so because of social pressures from peers, family, media, as well as internal pressure. This theory proposes that students are highly prone to the social influences from peers, family, media as well as internal pressure. Some gender differences in social influence is also reported in the literature. For example, the theory suggests that girls are more influenced by family members smoking than boys'. Girls have more smoking friends than boys, and girls are more likely to report future intentions to smoke when they have many friends that smoke regularly (Roosmalen & Daniel, 1989). These authors also pointed out that the peer groups of girls tend to be smaller which may promote greater conformity, girls may be more concerned about rejection from peers and that the pressure to use drugs is likely to be more indirect (through association with drug abusers) than direct. In terms of intervention, the social competency model proposes that student may engage in drug abuse because they lack psychosocial skills to deal with negative social influences (Ellickson et al., 1993; Botvin et al., 1990, 1995)

The strengths of Social Influence Theory is in the fact that It explains conformity and group behaviour and highlights the power of social norms and pressure; helps understands how attitudes and behaviours are shaped. It is useful in understanding social change and persuasion and recognizes the impact of social environment on individual behaviours and encourages critical thinking about social influences.

The theory is criticized on the ground that it overlooks individual differences and autonomy and underestimates the role of personal factors such as personality and values. It fails to account for resistance to social influence and neglects the impact of social influence on minority groups. The theory also makes it difficult to predict when and how influence occurs and its limited in explaining complex behaviours and decisions. It is further criticized for being too deterministic i.e. underestimating human agency, and lacks clear boundaries and definitions of key concepts. It is worthy of note that, social influence theory provides valuable insights into how social factors shape our behaviour and attitudes, but it should be considered in conjunction with other theories and perspectives to gain a more complete understanding of human behaviour.

Despite the limitations of this theory, it is relevant to the present study because taking cognizance of social pressures from peers, family, media as well as internal pressure as indicated in the theory, and helping student's resist these social pressures through improvement of their psychosocial skills, will help reduce the extent of drug abuse among students in tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Research Design

The study utilized survey research design. This is because it is the best method available to social scientists who are interested in collecting original data for the purpose of describing the population which is too large to observe directly.

Study Area

The study was carried out in three selected tertiary institutions in Kogi State Nigeria. These tertiary institutions include; Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba, Kogi State Polytechnic Lokoja, and Federal College of Education, Okene. Kogi State is one of the 36 States of Nigeria, located in the Nigerian Middle Belt. Created in 1991 from parts of Kwara State and Benue State, Kogi State is noted as being the only state in Nigeria to border ten other states. Kogi State is nicknamed "The Confluence State" due to the fact that the confluence of the River Niger and the River Benue occurs in its capital, Lokoja. Due to its strategic position in the middle of the country and its access to these major rivers, Kogi State is a key centre of commercial trade in Nigeria. Precisely, the study will be carried out across the three senatorial districts; Kogi East, Kogi Central and Kogi West.

There were 16 tertiary institutions in Kogi State (Kogi State Education Board, 2021). Across the three senatorial district, Kogi East senatorial districts tertiary institutions include; Prince Abubakar Audu University Anyigba, Federal Polytechnic Idah, Kogi State College of Education Ankpa, United Evangelical Church College of Nursing Ochadamu, Ofu LGA, Kogi State, Kogi State College of Nursing and Midwifery, Obangede, School of Nursing Egbe, Kogi State College of Health Sciences and Technology Idah and Central Polytechnic Ankpa. Kogi West senatorial district has; Federal University Lokoja, Kabba College of Agriculture, Salem University Lokoja, Kogi State Polytechnic Lokoja, Prime Polytechnic Lokoja and, Kogi State College of Education (Technical) Kabba. Kogi Central senatorial district has; Federal College of Education Okene and Confluence State University of Science and Technology Osara respectfully.

Brief Description of the Study Area

Prince Abubakar Audu University, (Formerly Kogi State University) located at Anyigba, is a state-owned university of Kogi, Nigeria. It was established in 1999 by Prince Abubakar Audu, the former governor of the state. At the time of its establishment, it was known as Kogi State University, It was later named Prince Abubakar Audu University (PAAU) in 2002, after the then sitting governor of Kogi State, who heralded its establishment, and later renamed Kogi State University (KSU) in 2003 by the former governor Ibrahim Idris and subsequently renamed as Prince Abubakar Audu University in 2020 by Governor Alhaji Yahaya Adoza Bello in respect of late Abubakar Audu the current Vice-Chancellor is Prof. Marietu Tenuche, Prince Abubakar Audu, Anyigba has 9 faculties, 1,120 staff.

Kogi State Polytechnic was established in December 1992 by the first and second Executive Governor of Kogi State, Prince Abubakar Audu through an amended edicts No. 6 of 1994. The polytechnic took off in January 1993 at the Government Science Secondary School, Lokoja and Osara Campus with Dr. Isa, I. A. as the first Rector. The mission of the institution is to produce skilled and competent manpower for commerce and industry using standard facilities and efficient personnel for the benefit of humanity. The institution is envisioned to establish institution where theory is blended with practice through imparting knowledge, which will culminate in shaping the individual and society.

Kogi State Polytechnic is located in Lokoja, Kogi State, Nigeria. It is owned and operated by Kogi State. As of 2007 it was accredited by the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) to give certificates in Art and printing, Business, Engineering, Finance and Science Computing at the National Diploma and Higher National Diploma levels. In December 2009 the polytechnic presented 16 programs for accreditation to a visiting team of NBTE officials, mainly for the new schools of Engineering and Environmental Technology, Applied Science and Management Studies.

Federal College of Education, Okene was established in 1974 At its inception, it was known as Federal Advanced Teachers College, Okene but it was renamed Federal College of Education, Okene in 1985. It was under the auspices of the Federal Ministry of Education up to 1987.

However, in 1987, the college assumed an autonomous status. Decree No.4 of the Federal Republic of Nigeria Gazette No.16, Vol.73 of 21st March made this college an autonomous institution; by implication, the highest policy making body now is the governing council of the college, which is constituted by the Federal Government.

Students are admitted from all over the country in fulfilment of the Federal Government's objective in setting up the college, which among others, is to serve as a unifying force among the various ethnic groups in Nigeria.

Population of the Study

The population for this research was students of all tertiary institutions in Kogi State, meanwhile, the target population for this study consisted of full-time students of selected tertiary educational institutions in Kogi State who enrolled for 2021/2022 academic session. The choice of this population is to assess the level of awareness both the returning and newly admitted students within the recent academic year. The population of this study consists of 15,884 students in Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba, 12,345 students in Kogi State Polytechnic Lokoja and 8,455 students in Federal College of Education, Okene. Hence, the total population for this study was 36,684 for the 2021/2022 academic session (Registry office of each tertiary institution, 2022).

The choice of Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba was because it is the first indigenous State University in Kogi State with a larger population of students situated in Anyigba being the centre of Igala land. The choice of Kogi State Polytechnic, Lokoja, was because is situated at the state headquarters, and students in such area have the tendency of involving in high level of drug abuse. Finally, the choice of Federal College of Education, Okene was because it is the most populated higher citadel of learning in the area which could feature more respondents to derive a valid conclusion in the area.

Table 1: Summary Distribution of Students Population by Institution

Tertiary Institution	Population of Students	Male	Female
Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba,	15,884	9,805	6,979
Kogi State Polytechnic Lokoja	12,345	3,580	8,765
Federal College of Education, Okene	8,455	2,098	6,357
Total	36,684	15,483	22,101

Source: Registry Office of each Tertiary Institution, 2023

3.4 Sample Size and Sampling Procedures

3.4.1 Sample Size and Determination

Sample size is the limited number of elements selected from a population which is a representative of the population. The sample size for this study was 396. This was determined using Taro Yamane's statistical formula as shown below:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

n = Sample size

N = Finite population

e = Level of significant or limit of tolerable error

$$n = \frac{36684}{1 + (36684)(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{36684}{1 + 91.71}$$

$$n = \frac{36684}{92.71}$$

$$n = 396$$

Therefore, the Sample size (n) = 396.

Sampling Techniques

The study utilized both probability and non-probability sampling techniques which comprises; purposive sampling, stratified random sampling and simple random sampling techniques. Purposive sampling was used in the selection of students in Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba in Kogi East Senatorial district, Kogi State Polytechnic Lokoja in Kogi West Senatorial district and Federal College of Education, Okene in Kogi Central senatorial district. Stratified sampling technique was used to categorize the study population into three strata. Hence all students were grouped into male and female according to their institutions. This enhanced the identification of sub-groups within the study population and also form a sample which adequately represented these sub-groups. Then simple random sampling technique was used to ensure that each member of the population had equal chance of being selected for the study.

Table 2: Distribution of Sample Size by Institutions

Tertiary Institution	Population of Students	Sample Size
Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba,	15,884	$396 \times 15884 / 36684 = 171$
Kogi State Polytechnic Lokoja	12,345	$396 \times 12345 / 36684 = 133$
Federal College of Education, Okene	8,455	$396 \times 8455 / 36684 = 92$
Total	36,684	396

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2023

The final respondents for this work were selected randomly because it gives each respondents an equal chance of been represented in the study.

Methods of Data Collection

This study adopted quantitative method of data gathering.

Sources of Data

The study utilized mainly primary source of data collection. Primary data sources include; survey, observations, questionnaire, focus group discussion and interviews. However, the primary source for this study deals with collection of data using questionnaire directly from the students being the respondents for the study.

Instruments of Data Collection/Administration

A semi-structured self-administered questionnaire was used for the study and it was divided into three parts. The first part was a cover letter explaining the purpose of the survey and requesting for voluntary participation. The second part contained the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents such as age, religion, sex, etc. while the third part aimed at gathering information regarding respondents' perception on the socio-psychological effects of drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions in Kogi state. The questionnaire items were mainly closed ended questions which helped to collect information on quantitative data. The closed ended questions prompted the respondents to provide fixed answers by choosing suitable answers. Thus, the researcher distributed 396 copies of the questionnaire across the three selected tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria. The questions in the questionnaire were categorized based on five-likert scale of; Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Strongly Disagree (2) and Disagree (1). The questionnaire was administered to the respondents directly by the researcher and collated after they have been duly filled and retrieved by the respondents.

Reliability and Validity of Research Instrument

Table 3: Validity of Research Instrument

Measure Name	Number of Items	Item Communalities range	Construct Validity (Item total Correlation range)	KMO Measure of Variable Adequacy
Awareness of Drug Abuse and Effects of drug abuse	3	0.77 - 0.86	0.73 - 0.82	0.81
Drug Usage	8	0.70 - 0.96	0.74 - 0.87	0.88
Types of Drugs Commonly Abused	16	0.70 - 0.86	0.70 - 0.89	0.86
Factors Responsible for Drug Abuse	8	0.71 - 0.87	0.73 - 0.85	0.77
Social Effects of Drug Abuse	10	0.74 - 0.92	0.71 - 0.83	0.82
Psychological Effects of Drug Abuse	12	0.75 - 0.84	0.75 - 0.87	0.84

Based on Table 3, six different measures (Awareness of Drug Abuse and Effects of drug abuse, Drug Usage, Types of Drugs Commonly Abused, Factors Responsible for Drug Abuse, Social Effects of Drug Abuse, and Psychological Effects of Drug Abuse) that were used to assess various aspects of drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria. For each measure, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was used where the item communalities and item loading was obtained at figures between 0.70 to 0.96 which is considered acceptable (El hajjar, 2018); also, inter-item correlation or item total correlation using bivariate analysis was used to determine construct validity and figures obtained ranged between 0.70 to 0.86 which was also considered acceptable (Robinson et al., 1991); while Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) was used to measure variable adequacy to which figures range of 0.77 to 0.88 obtained were acceptable (Beaves et al., 2013).

In this study, all the measures have good content validity, which means that the items in the measures accurately represent the content domain of drug abuse among students in Kogi State, Nigeria. The

measures also have good construct validity, which means that they accurately measure the underlying constructs or concepts they are intended to measure. Furthermore, the measures have acceptable criterion validity, which means that they are related to external criteria or standards of drug abuse among students in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Reliability of the Research Instruments

Measure Name	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Awareness and Effects of Drug Abuse	3	0.75
Drug Usage	8	0.73
Types of Drugs Commonly Abused	16	0.81
Factors Responsible for Drug Abuse	8	0.79
Social Effects of Drug Abuse	10	0.87
Psychological Effects of Drug Abuse	12	0.78

Table 4 showed the five different measures (Drug Usage, Types of Drugs Commonly Abused, Factors Responsible for Drug Abuse, Social Effects of Drug Abuse, and Psychological Effects of Drug Abuse) that were used to assess various aspects of drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria. For each measure, the study conducted a reliability test using Cronbach's Alpha as the reliability coefficient. The table 4.2 showed the number of items in each measure and the corresponding Cronbach's Alpha value, which indicates the internal consistency of each measure. Note that a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.70 or higher is generally considered acceptable for research purposes. In this study, all the measures have a Cronbach's Alpha value greater than 0.70, which suggests that they are reliable measures for assessing the various aspects of drug abuse among students in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Methods of Data Analysis

The study used descriptive statistics of mean analysis to achieve objectives one to three of the study. The choice of the descriptive statistics of mean analysis technique is because it explains the characteristics of the individual data, and helps in decision analysis in the process of achieving the objectives of the study. All the hypotheses stated were tested with one-way ANOVA because the study ascertained the influence of the independent variables (Social and psychological well-being of students) on the dependent variable (drug usage).

Criteria for Inclusion and Exclusion

The inclusion criteria were all students on full time programme of selected tertiary educational institutions in Kogi State who enrolled for 2021/2022 academic session; students who were both below 16 years of age and those above; both female and male students who might have indulged or presumed to be indulging in drug abuse and were willing to participate in the study in their various institutions of learning. While the exclusion criteria were all students who have not enrolled for the 2021/2022 academic session and those who declined participation in the study and students who were ill.

Ethical Consideration

In carrying out a systematic study of this nature, ethical consideration is sacrosanct. This is because it is one of the most important points that deserve attention. The researcher therefore was guided by the ethics of conducting research to protect the image of the respondents by treating their responses with

strictly confidentially and strictly for this academic purpose. Informed consent was also obtained from the study respondents verbally or orally. The researcher obtained permission from the relevant authorities in the tertiary institutions before the research activity was carried out. Ethical clearance certificate was sought and obtained from the Ethics and Research Committee of the Prince Abubakar Audu University's College of Health Science (See the approved number: CHSREC/2023/0009 dated 10th July, 2023).

Data Presentation and Analysis

A total of 396 copies of questionnaire were administered to the respondents across the three tertiary institutions in Kogi State of Nigeria. After concerted follow up efforts, 360 copies were duly completed and retrieved, translating to 90% response rate. Therefore, the researcher used 360 copies of the questionnaire for the presentation and analysis of data.

Table 5: Percentage distribution of respondents' socio-demographic characteristics

Variables		PAAU	KSP	FCOE	Total (360)	Percentage (90%)
Sex	Male	121(30.2)	91(22.7)	63(15.7)	275	68.8
	Female	40(10)	21(5.2)	24(6.0)	85	21.2
Religion	Christianity	80(22.3)	44(12.2)	30(8.3)	154	42.8
	Islam	75(20.8)	66(18.3)	60(16.7)	201	55.8
	African traditional religion	3(0.8)	1(0.3)	1(0.3)	5	1.4
Age (in years)	Below 16 years	40(10)	15(3.8)	11(2.8)	66	16.5
	16-20 years	101(25.3)	60(15.0)	48(2.0)	209	52.3
	21-25 years	30(7.5)	15(3.8)	7(1.7)	52	13.0
	26 and above	20(5.0)	7(1.7)	6(1.5)	33	8.2
Tertiary institution		161 (44.7)	112(31.1)	87(24.2)	360	90
Level of study	NCE 1	-	-	21	21	5.8
	NCE 2	-	-	34	34	9.4
	NCE 3	-	-	32	32	8.9
	ND 1	-	28	-	28	7.7
	ND 2	-	18	-	18	5.0
	HND 1	-	41	-	41	11.3
	HND 2	-	25	-	25	6.9
	100 level	28	-	-	28	7.8
	200 level	32	-	-	32	8.9
	300 level	36	-	-	36	10.0
	400 level	65	-	-	65	18.1

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 5 shows that 275(68.8%) respondents were male while 85 (21.2%) were female. This shows that the majority of the respondents from the selected tertiary institutions were male. In terms of religion 154 (42.8%) respondents were into Christianity. 201 (55.8%) were into Islam and 5(1.4%) were into African traditional religion. Considering the age of respondents, 46(12.8%) were below 16 years, 189 (52.5%) were 16-20 years, 52(14.4%) were 21-25 years, 31 (8.6%) were 26 years and above. Considering the tertiary institution of respondents, 161 (44.7%) were from Prince Abubakar Audu University, 112 (31.1%) were from Kogi State Polytechnic and 87 (24.2%) were from Kogi

State College of Education. The results for the level of study showed that 21 (5.8%) of the respondents were in NCE 1, 34 (9.4%) in NCE 2, 32 (8.9%) in NCE 3, 28(7.7%) in ND 1, 18 (5.0%) in ND 2, 41(11.3%) in HND 1, 25(6.9%) in HND 2, 28(7.8%) in 100 level, 32(8.9%) in 200 level, 36 (10.0%) in 300 level and 65 (18.1%) in 400 level.

From the table above, it is seen that majority of the respondents were males and are also within the ages of 16-20, this indicates that the respondents are within the knowledgeable and active age. This is because most people who engage in drug abuse are within this age bracket.

Research Question 1: What is the extent of students of tertiary educational institutions' awareness of the socio-psychological effects of drug abuse in Kogi State, Nigeria?

Table 6: Awareness of the socio-psychological effects of Drug Abuse among Tertiary Institution Students in Kogi State

Items	Frequency N= 360	Percentage (%)
Do you know anything about drug abuse?		
Yes	114	31.7
No	246	68.3
Do you use drug other than prescribed by health care practitioners?		
Yes	282	78.3
No	78	21.7
Are you aware of the socio-psychological effects of drug abuse?		
Aware	114	31.7
Not aware	214	59.4
Don't know	32	8.9

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 6 shows that 114 (31.7%) of the respondents know about drug abuse while 246 (68.3%) have do not know about drug abuse. This implied that larger percentage of respondents across the tertiary institutions do not have knowledge of drug abuse. It also showed that 282 (78.3%) of the respondents use drug other than prescribed by health care practitioners while 78 (21.7%) do not use drug other than the one prescribed by health care practitioners. This implied that larger percentage of the respondents made use of drug other than the one prescribed by health practitioners. The table also revealed that 114 (31.7%) of the respondents were aware of the socio-psychological effects of drug abuse. 214 (59.4%) of the respondents were not aware of the socio-psychological effects of drug abuse. Also, 32 (8.9%) of the respondents don't know the socio-psychological effects of drug abuse. This implied that larger percentage of the respondents were not aware of the socio-psychological effects of drug abuse.

Table 7: Mean Analysis of drug use among Students of Tertiary Institutions in Kogi State

S/N	Drugs	5	4	3	2	1	Total	Mean	Remark
1	I use drugs daily	120 33.3%	100 27.7%	80 22.2%	35 9.7%	25 6.9%	360	3.7	Accepted
2	I use drugs because it gives me confidence	125 34.7%	95 23.4%	75 20.8%	45 12.5%	20 5.6%	360	3.7	Accepted
3	I use drugs because it put me on	100 27.7%	90 25%	80 22.2%	75 20.8%	15 4.2%	360	3.5	Accepted

	high morals								
4	Drugs are very useful to me because it gives me great feelings	140 38.9%	90 25%	80 22.2%	30 8.3%	20 5.6%	360	3.8	Accepted
5	Drugs are important because it gives inspirations	130 36.1%	100 27.7%	80 22.2%	40 11.1%	20 5.6%	360	3.9	Accepted
6	Drugs is useful because to enhance performance	120 33.3%	110 30.6%	60 16.7%	40 11.1%	30 8.3%	360	3.6	Accepted
7	It looks like my drugs intake is on the increase	100 27.7%	90 25%	80 22.2%	75 20.8%	15 4.2%	360	3.5	Accepted
8	I depend on drugs to perform better	130 36.1%	100 27.7%	80 22.2%	40 11.1%	20 5.6%	360	3.9	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Keys: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Strongly Disagree (2), Disagree (1)

Table 7 above presents mean analysis of descriptive statistics and therefore makes the following decisions. The decision criterion employed was to accept any statement with mean score of 3.0 and above and reject those with less than 3.0 based on the likert scale of 1 to 5. For this reason, since the mean scores of all the functions suggested in Table 4.6 are all greater than 3.0, it therefore implied their acceptance. Thus, in terms of drug usage, most of the respondents use drugs daily, use drugs because it gives them confidence, use drugs because it put them on high morals, use drugs it gives them great feelings, use drugs it gives them inspirations and use drugs because it helps to enhance performance.

Research Question 2: What are the types of drugs commonly abused by students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria?

Table 8: Mean Analysis of Type of Drugs Commonly Abused among Students of Tertiary Institutions in Kogi State

S/N	Types of drugs	5	4	3	2	1	Total	Mean	Remark
1	Indian hemp	120 33.3%	100 27.7%	80 22.2%	35 9.7%	25 6.9%	360	3.7	Accepted
2	Tobacco	125 34.7%	95 23.4%	75 20.8%	45 12.5%	20 5.6%	360	3.7	Accepted
3	Cocaine and morphine	100 27.7%	90 25%	80 22.2%	75 20.8%	15 4.2%	360	3.5	Accepted
4	Heroin and Caffeine	140 38.9%	90 25%	80 22.2%	30 8.3%	20 5.6%	360	3.8	Accepted
5	Tramadol	130 36.1%	100 27.7%	80 22.2%	40 11.1%	20 5.6%	360	3.9	Accepted
6	Codeine	120 33.3%	110 30.6%	60 16.7%	40 11.1%	30 8.3%	360	3.6	Accepted
7	alcohol-ethanol	100 27.7%	90 25%	80 22.2%	75 20.8%	15 4.2%	360	3.5	Accepted
8	Tranquilizer	120 33.3%	110 30.6%	60 16.7%	40 11.1%	30 8.3%	360	3.6	Accepted

9.	Inhalants	120 33.3%	100 27.7%	80 22.2%	35 9.7%	25 6.9%	360	3.7	Accepted
10.	Madras	125 34.7%	95 23.4%	75 20.8%	45 12.5%	20 5.6%	360	3.7	Accepted
11	Glue	100 27.7%	90 25%	80 22.2%	75 20.8%	15 4.2%	360	3.5	Accepted
12	Barbiturates/ Amphetamines	140 38.9%	90 25%	80 22.2%	30 8.3%	20 5.6%	360	3.8	Accepted
13	Morphine	100 27.7%	90 25%	80 22.2%	75 20.8%	15 4.2%	360	3.5	Accepted
14	Ephedrine	120 33.3%	110 30.6%	60 16.7%	40 11.1%	30 8.3%	360	3.6	Accepted
15	Librium	125 34.7%	95 23.4%	75 20.8%	45 12.5%	20 5.6%	360	3.7	Accepted
16	Dexamphetamine	100 27.7%	90 25%	80 22.2%	75 20.8%	15 4.2%	360	3.5	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Keys: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Strongly Disagree (2), Disagree (1)

Table 8 above presents mean analysis of descriptive statistics and therefore makes the following decision. The decision criterion employed was to accept any statement with mean score of 3.0 and above and reject those with less than 3.0 based on the likert scale of 1 to 5. For this reason, since the mean scores of all the types of drugs suggested in Table 4.7 are all greater than 3.0, it therefore implied their acceptance. Hence, the types of drugs commonly abused include; Indian hemp, Tobacco, Cocaine and morphine, Heroine and Caffeine, Tramadol, Codeine, alcohol-ethanol, Tranquilizer, Inhalants, Madras, Glue, Barbiturates and Amphetamines, Morphine, Ephedrine, Librium and Dexamphetamine. However, the most commonly abused one in the selected tertiary institutions was Tramadol because it has the highest mean score of 3.9.

Research Question 3: What are the factors responsible for drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria?

Table 9: Mean Analysis of Factors Responsible for Drug Abuse among Students of Tertiary Institutions in Kogi State

S/N	Drugs	5	4	3	2	1	Total	Mean	Remark
1	Place of residence	120 33.3%	100 27.7%	80 22.2%	35 9.7%	25 6.9%	360	3.7	Accepted
2	Income level	125 34.7%	95 23.4%	75 20.8%	45 12.5%	20 5.6%	360	3.7	Accepted
3	peer group influence	130 36.1%	100 27.7%	80 22.2%	40 11.1%	20 5.6%	360	3.9	Accepted
4	level of school security management	140 38.9%	90 25%	80 22.2%	30 8.3%	20 5.6%	360	3.8	Accepted
5	Religion	100 27.7%	90 25%	80 22.2%	75 20.8%	15 4.2%	360	3.5	Accepted
6	Education level	120 33.3%	110 30.6%	60 16.7%	40 11.1%	30 8.3%	360	3.6	Accepted
7	experimental curiosity	100 27.7%	90 25%	80 22.2%	75 20.8%	15 4.2%	360	3.5	Accepted
8	lack of parental supervision	130 36.1%	100 27.7%	80 22.2%	40 11.1%	20 5.6%	360	3.9	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Keys: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Strongly Disagree (2), Disagree (1)

Table 9 above presents mean analysis of descriptive statistics makes the following decision rule. The decision criterion employed was to accept any statement with mean score of 3.0 and above and reject those with less than 3.0 based on the likert scale of 1 to 5. For this reason, since the mean scores of all the factors suggested in Table 4.8 are all greater than 3.0, it therefore implied their acceptance. Thus, the factors responsible for drug abuse include; place of residence, income level, peer group influence, level of school security management, religion, education level, experimental curiosity and lack of parental supervision.

Research Question 4: What are the social effects of drug abuse on the students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria?

Table 10: Mean Analysis of Social Effects of Drug Abuse among Students of Tertiary Institutions in Kogi State

S/N	Social effects	5	4	3	2	1	Total	Mean	Remark
1	Dropping out of school	100 27.7%	90 25%	80 22.2%	75 20.8%	15 4.2%	360	3.5	Accepted
2	Shame and guilt	125 34.7%	95 23.4%	75 20.8%	45 12.5%	20 5.6%	360	3.7	Accepted
3	Embarrassment	100 27.7%	90 25%	80 22.2%	75 20.8%	15 4.2%	360	3.5	Accepted
4	Sleeplessness or insomnia	140 38.9%	90 25%	80 22.2%	30 8.3%	20 5.6%	360	3.8	Accepted
5	Less of coordination	130 36.1%	100 27.7%	80 22.2%	40 11.1%	20 5.6%	360	3.9	Accepted
6	Slurred speech	120 33.3%	110 30.6%	60 16.7%	40 11.1%	30 8.3%	360	3.6	Accepted
7	Temporary sense of euphoria or joy	100 27.7%	90 25%	80 22.2%	75 20.8%	15 4.2%	360	3.5	Accepted
8	Relationship problem	120 33.3%	110 30.6%	60 16.7%	40 11.1%	30 8.3%	360	3.6	Accepted
9.	Poor work ethics or academic performance	120 33.3%	100 27.7%	80 22.2%	35 9.7%	25 6.9%	360	3.7	Accepted
10.	Difficulty maintaining personal hygiene	125 34.7%	95 23.4%	75 20.8%	45 12.5%	20 5.6%	360	3.7	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Keys: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Strongly Disagree (2), Disagree (1)

Table 10 above presents the mean analysis of descriptive statistics and therefore makes the following decision. The decision criterion employed was to accept any statement with mean score of 3.0 and above and reject those with less than 3.0 based on the likert scale of 1 to 5. For this reason, since the mean scores of all the social effects suggested in Table 4.7 are all greater than 3.0, it therefore implied their acceptance. Hence, the social effects of drug abuse include; dropping out of school, shame and guilt, embarrassment, sleeplessness or insomnia, less of coordination, slurred speech, temporary sense of euphoria or joy, relationship problem, poor work ethics or academic performance and difficulty maintaining personal hygiene.

Research Question 5: What are the social effects of drug abuse on the students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria?

Table 11: Mean Analysis Psychological Effects of Drug Abuse among Students of Tertiary Institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria

S/N	psychological effects	5	4	3	2	1	Total	Mean	Remark
1	Mental illness	100 27.7%	90 25%	80 22.2%	75 20.8%	15 4.2%	360	3.5	Accepted
2	Heart attacks	125 34.7%	95 23.4%	75 20.8%	45 12.5%	20 5.6%	360	3.7	Accepted
3	Anger	100 27.7%	90 25%	80 22.2%	75 20.8%	15 4.2%	360	3.5	Accepted
4	Frustration	140 38.9%	90 25%	80 22.2%	30 8.3%	20 5.6%	360	3.8	Accepted
5	Anxiety	130 36.1%	100 27.7%	80 22.2%	40 11.1%	20 5.6%	360	3.9	Accepted
6	Worry	120 33.3%	110 30.6%	60 16.7%	40 11.1%	30 8.3%	360	3.6	Accepted
7	Stress and depression	100 27.7%	90 25%	80 22.2%	75 20.8%	15 4.2%	360	3.5	Accepted
8	Panic disorder	120 33.3%	110 30.6%	60 16.7%	40 11.1%	30 8.3%	360	3.6	Accepted
9.	Increased aggregation	120 33.3%	100 27.7%	80 22.2%	35 9.7%	25 6.9%	360	3.7	Accepted
10.	Memory loss	125 34.7%	95 23.4%	75 20.8%	45 12.5%	20 5.6%	360	3.7	Accepted
11.	Difficulty in concentration	100 27.7%	90 25%	80 22.2%	75 20.8%	15 4.2%	360	3.5	Accepted
12.	Lethargy or loss of interest	140 38.9%	90 25%	80 22.2%	30 8.3%	20 5.6%	360	3.8	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Keys: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Strongly Disagree (2), Disagree (1)

Table 11 above presents the mean analysis of descriptive statistics and therefore makes the following decision. The decision criterion employed was to accept any statement with mean score of 3.0 and above and reject those with less than 3.0 based on the likert scale of 1 to 5. For this reason, since the mean scores of all the psychological effects suggested in Table 4.7 are all greater than 3.0, it therefore implied their acceptance. Hence, the psychological effects of drug abuse include; mental illness, heart attacks, anger, frustration, anxiety, worry, stress and depression, panic disorder, increased aggregation, memory loss, difficulty in concentration and lethargy or loss of interest.

Hypotheses Testing:

Hypothesis One

H₀: Awareness of socio-psychological effects of drug abuse do not deter its usage among students of selected tertiary educational institution in Kogi State, Nigeria.

H₁: Awareness of socio-psychological effects of drug abuse deter its usage among students of selected tertiary educational institution in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Decision Rule:

The decision rule for all the hypotheses used for this study is that if F-calculated is greater than the F-Critical also known as the table value, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis but if the F-Calculated is lesser than the F-Critical, we accept the null hypothesis.

Table 12: One-Way ANOVA showing influence of the awareness of socio-psychological effects of drug abuse on its usage among students of tertiary educational institution in Kogi State

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	12.62	4	3.15	1.92	0.0691
Within Groups	9.84	6	1.64		
Total	39.46	10			

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 12 shows that the significance value (0.0691) of the F-statistic (1.92) was greater than 0.05. The study accepted the alternative hypothesis and rejected the null hypothesis. Hence, it was concluded that awareness of socio-psychological effects of drug abuse do deter its usage among students of tertiary educational institution in Kogi State, Nigeria

Hypothesis two

H₀: There are no gender differences in commonly abused drugs among students of tertiary educational institution in Kogi State, Nigeria.

H₁: There are gender differences in commonly abused drugs among students of tertiary educational institution in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Table 13: One-Way ANOVA showing gender differences in commonly abused drugs among students of tertiary educational institution in Kogi State

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	54.73	4	13.68	6.71	.0201
Within Groups	12.23	6	2.04		
Total	66.96	10			

Source: Researcher's Computation using SPSS version 20.0, 2023

Table 13 shows that the significance value (0.0201) of F-Statistic (6.71) was greater than 0.05. The study rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis. Hence, it was concluded that there were gender differences in commonly abused drugs among students of tertiary educational institution in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis three

H₀: Availability and accessibility of drugs do not influence its abuse among students in tertiary educational institution in Kogi State, Nigeria.

H₁: Availability and accessibility of drugs influence its abuse among students in tertiary educational institution in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Table 14: One-Way ANOVA of the influence of Availability and accessibility of drugs on its abuse among students in tertiary educational institution in Kogi State

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	84.18	4	21.05	8.19	.0001
Within Groups	15.44	6	2.57		
Total	99.62	10			

Source: Researcher's Computation using SPSS version 20.0, 2023

Table 14 shows that the significance value (0.0001) of F-Statistic (8.19) was greater than 0.05. The study rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis. Hence, it was concluded that availability and accessibility of drugs influence abuse among students in tertiary educational institution in Kogi State, Nigeria

Hypothesis four

H₀: Drug abuse does not significantly lead to social effects among students in tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria

H₁: Drug abuse does not significantly lead to social effects among students in tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria

Table 15: One-Way ANOVA showing the influence of Drug abuse on social effects among students in tertiary institutions in Kogi State

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	42.12	4	10.53	4.83	0.0041
Within Groups	13.10	6	2.18		
Total	55.22	10			

Source: Researcher's Computation using SPSS version 20.0, 2023

Table 15 shows that the significance value (0.0041) of F-Statistic (4.83) was greater than 0.05. The study rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis. Hence, it was concluded that drug abuse significantly led to social effects among students in tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis five

H₀: Drug abuse does not significantly lead to psychological effects among students in tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria

H₁: Drug abuse does not significantly lead to psychological effects among students in tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Table 16: One-way ANOVA result showing the influence of Drug abuse psychological effects among students in tertiary institutions in Kogi State

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	73.34	4	12.22	3.97	.0321
Within Groups	18.46	6	3.08		
Total	91.80	10			

Source: Researcher's Computation using SPSS version 20.0, 2023

Table 16 shows that the significance value (0.0321) of F-Statistic (3.97) was greater than 0.05. The study rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis. Hence, it was concluded that drug abuse significantly lead to psychological effects among students in tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Major Findings

The study examined the socio-psychological effects of drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria. The results of the five objectives raised for the study are discussed thus:

The objective one was to determine the extent of students of tertiary educational institutions awareness of drug abuse in Kogi State, Nigeria. Based on the result, it was found that larger percentage of respondents across the tertiary institutions did not have knowledge of drug abuse, also larger percentage (78.3%) of the respondents made use of drug other than the one prescribed by health practitioners and as such larger percentage of the respondents were not aware of the socio-psychological effects of drug abuse. This finding is similar to that of Udoh, Chukwueke and Okafor (2020) who revealed that most students are not aware of the consequence of drug abuse.

The objective two was to identify the type of drugs commonly abused among students in among students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria. based on the results, in terms of drug usage, most of the respondents used drugs daily, used drugs because it gives them confidence, used drugs because it put them on high morals, used drugs it gives them great feelings, used drugs it gives them inspirations and use drugs because it helps to enhance performance. Specifically, it was discovered that vast of types of drugs abused included; Indian hemp, Tobacco, Cocaine and morphine, Heroine and Caffeine, Tramadol, Codeine, alcohol-ethanol, Tranquilizer, Inhalants, Madras, Glue, Barbiturates and Amphetamines, Morphine, Ephedrine, Librium and Dexamphetamine. However, the most commonly abused one in the selected tertiary institutions was Tramadol.

This finding is in line with that of Oshikoya and Alli (2016) who revealed that majority of the students ignorantly depend on one form of drug or the other (such as Tobacco, Indian hemp, cocaine, morphine, Heroine, Alcohol, ephedrine, Madras, Caffeine, Glue, Barbiturates and Amphetamines) for their various daily activities. It is also in line with that of Okoza and Aluede (2019) who identified drugs substances commonly abused to include; alcohol, kolanut, tobacco, cannabis, Librium, dexamphetamine, reactivan, mandrax, Chinese capsule, cocaine and Lysergic acid Diethylamide (LSD). It is also similar to that of Udoh, Chukwueke and Okafor (2020) who observed type of drugs abused to include; alcohol-ethanol, tobacco, tramadol to be commonly abused by students. The finding is also similar to that of Marygoretty and Adhiambo (2021) who indicated that most of the students used Tobacco, Miraa, Cocaine, Tranquilizers, Kuber and Marijuana. However, relating this current finding to that of Oluyemi, Adejoke, Olaoluwajubeelo, Deborah, Motolani, Lateefat and Gbenga (2019), identified these drugs to include; alcohol, tobacco, Cocaine, Coffee, Codeine, tranquilizer and Inhalants in that order, but Bawa (2015) viewed most commonly abused substance to include Marijuana and the least abused was cocaine, the reasons were availability and affordability of these substances. Alcohol was not commonly abused due to religious prohibition. This findings is also supported by the social influence theory. The theory states that drug and substance intake by students are learnt from parents and peer who are very influential to the students (Bandura, 1977).

The objective three was to identify the factors responsible for drug abuse among students in tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria. Based on the results, it was found that the factors responsible for drug abuse were; place of residence, income level, peer group influence, level of school security management, religion, education level, experimental curiosity and lack of parental supervision. This finding is similar to that of Aremu, Shehu and Bomanm (2018) who revealed Factors such as; experimental curiosity, lack of parental supervision and socio-economic conditions of the students are responsible for drug abuse among students in tertiary institutions. However, in line with that finding according to Afolabi (2017), factors such as place of residence, location of students, income, peer group influence, level of school security management were considered as major factors influencing drug abuse among students. The finding is also similar to that by Kuku and Odusanya (2015) who revealed factors that trigger drug abuse to include; education level and religion. However, it is similar to that of Olurunfemi and Faleke (2020) who also viewed factors such as; shame of disclosing their problem to the doctor, ignorance, cultural and socioeconomic issues as the reasons for increase in drug abuse in Nigeria. The finding is similar to that of Gray (2012) who revealed one of the strongest social reasons for people under involvement in drug abuse is peer group. Both teenager and adults are involved. Such peer influence is characterized by the desire to be accepted among friends or in social circumstance. Many of the students, who use hard drug, obtain them from friends in the same school or neighbouring schools. Such drugs are used at social gathering or when students have symptoms of sickness or stay awake during examination. This finding is further supported by Social Development Theory which explained that the influence of individual characteristics and personality traits on drug use deviance (Hawkins & Weis 2002).

The objective four was to assess the social effects of drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria. Based on the results, it was found that the social effects of drug abuse include; dropping out of school, shame and guilt, embarrassment, sleeplessness or insomnia, less of coordination, slurred speech, temporary sense of euphoria or joy, relationship problem, poor work ethics or academic performance and difficulty maintaining personal hygiene.

Furthermore, objective five was to evaluate the psychological effects of drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria. The results showed that the psychological effects of drug abuse include; mental illness, heart attacks, anger, frustration, anxiety, worry, stress and depression, panic disorder, increased aggregation, memory loss, difficulty in concentration and lethargy or loss of interest.

Based on hypotheses tested, it was concluded that awareness of socio-psychological effects of drug abuse do deter its usage among students of tertiary educational institution in Kogi State, Nigeria. Also, it was concluded that there were gender differences in commonly abused drugs among students of tertiary educational institution in Kogi State, Nigeria. It was generalized that availability and accessibility of drugs influence abuse among students in tertiary educational institution in Kogi State, Nigeria. In addition, it was concluded that drug abuse significantly lead to social effects among students in tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria. Finally, it was concluded that drug abuse significantly lead to psychological effects among students in tertiary institutions in Kogi State, Nigeria. The social Development and Social influence theories further strengthened the this findings in that the combine factors of individual characteristics and personality traits, parental influence and peer pressure, frustration and strain together cause spur students into taking using and abusing drugs on campus.

Conclusion

Drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions in Kogi state, Nigeria has high level of the socio-psychological effects. However, it was generalized based on the findings that larger percentage students across the tertiary institutions had no knowledge of drug abuse, larger percentage of the students made use of drug other than the one prescribed by health practitioners and larger percentage of the students were not aware of the socio-psychological effects of drug abuse. In terms of drug usage, most of the students used drugs daily, use drugs because it gives them confidence, use drugs because it put them on high morals, use drugs it gives them great feelings, use drugs it gives them inspirations and use drugs because it helps to enhance performance. Specifically, it was concluded that vast of types of drugs were abused by the students. However, the most commonly abused one in the selected tertiary institutions was Tramadol.

It was also concluded that the factors responsible for drug abuse were; place of residence, income level, peer group influence, level of school security management, religion, education level, experimental curiosity and lack of parental supervision. In addition, it was inferred that the social effects of drug abuse were; dropping out of school, shame and guilt, embarrassment, sleeplessness or insomnia, less of coordination, slurred speech, temporary sense of euphoria or joy, relationship problem, poor work ethics or academic performance and difficulty maintaining personal hygiene. Finally, it was concluded that the psychological effects of drug abuse included; mental illness, heart attacks, anger, frustration, anxiety, worry, stress and depression, panic disorder, increased aggregation, memory loss, difficulty in concentration and lethargy or loss of interest.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings. These include:

1. Government through the management of the tertiary institutions should engage students in order to inform their knowledge of drug abuse as well as create aware of the socio-psychological effects of drug abuse.
2. Government at all levels through the management of the tertiary institutions should prohibit an act that could lead to sales of vast types of drugs commonly abused by the students especially Tramadol in order to cushion its socio-psychological effects among the students.
3. Government at all levels through the management of the tertiary institution should put into consideration factors responsible for drug abuse such as; place of residence, income level, peer group influence, level of school security management, religion, education level, experimental curiosity and lack of parental supervision when making plausible decision on control of drug abuse among students.
4. The management of the tertiary institution should continue to inform the students through seminars and workshops on the social effects of drug abuse such as; dropping out of school, shame and guilt, embarrassment, sleeplessness or insomnia, less of coordination, slurred speech, temporary sense of euphoria or joy, relationship problem, poor work ethics or academic performance and difficulty maintaining personal hygiene towards reducing its usage among them.
5. The school management should also inform the students through awareness creation on the psychological effects of drug abuse such as; mental illness, heart attacks, anger, frustration, anxiety, worry, stress and depression, panic disorder, increased aggregation, memory loss,

difficulty in concentration and lethargy or loss of interest towards reducing its usage among them.

6. The National Drug Law Enforcement Agency should initiate a collaborative programme with school managements in Kogi State to continuously sensitize students through participatory methods about the hazardous effects of drug experimentation and gradual addiction and dependence. This programme will drastically reduce the socio-psychological effects of drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions in Kogi State.

Limitations of the Study

The progress of this study was hindered by certain constraints, some of which includes: technical factors such as power supply which have limited the speed of the researcher in carrying out this research work and have subjected the researcher to sourcing power from substitute power supplies such as generator sets and power banks. Furthermore, financial constraints which have restricted the researcher from getting a wide range of materials for the study as the researcher narrow down its respondents in a bid to reduce the cost at which the questionnaires were printed, also, resulting from financial constraints. However, the researcher is able to solve the financial constraint by resulting to borrowings from friends and family members to further the research work.

Suggestion for Further Study

Based on the limitations of the study, the following area of research interests were suggested for future researchers. These include;

- i. Effects of Drug Abuse and Self-Medication Practice on Health Status of Households in Kogi State
- ii. Socio-Psychological Effects of Drug Abuse and Students Academic Performance in Kogi State.
- iii. Effects of Drug Abuse on Socio-Economic Development among Graduates in Kogi State.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declared no conflict of interests regarding this research work.

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Authors' Contributions

Mary **IBOBOR** carried out the entire research work.

Edime **YUNUSA** reviewed the manuscript and analyzed parts of the data

Prof. Julius Olugbenga **OWOYEMI** supervised the research work.

Dr. Thomas Imoudu **GOMMENT** reviewed and perused the manuscript.

All authors proofread and approved the final manuscript.

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